

METHODOLOGY FOR ASSESSING EFFECTIVE PERSONNEL MANAGEMENT MECHANISMS IN ENTERPRISES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7927941>

Abstract. *Determination of optimal organizational and economic mechanisms of personnel management in enterprises, significant factors, management and effective use of personnel, analysis of basic direction of personnel management. With the effective use of the human capital involved in the production, it is advisable for the subjects of the employer-enterprise to take into account the emotional and psychological states of human capital.*

Keywords: *Personnel management, personnel management efficiency, human capital, motivation, organizational and economic mechanisms.*

In the process of deepening market relations, economic liberalization and globalization in our country, new activities and new ways of thinking are required. Because the employees of the enterprise are well aware of the specific features of optimal use of existing conditions, further development of innovative activities and economic growth of the country, increase of financial resources of enterprises and organizations and providing them with funds, different from the economic point of view, drawing conclusions should be able to prove that they are correct and reasonable.

Since the main object of management is employees, in the process of managing a modern organization, the main attention is paid to the activities of employees, their mutual relations, interests, and ways of achieving goals.

At the enterprise level, regardless of the form of the property and the attitude towards it, it is important to rationally organize the management system of employees in order for employees to work effectively and to use their physical and mental potential to the full and to achieve the goals set for each organization.

Based on the fact that the organization and effective management of the production process in a market economy is an urgent problem, in order to ensure the effective use of human capital, the essence of raising its intellectual level was emphasized by economists, including Thomas J. Peters, Robert H. Waterman [1] books, based on the analysis of advanced developing US companies, employee motivation, simplicity of the organizational structure, maintaining close and reliable relationships with customers who purchase the company's products, independent organization and production management by enterprise managers show the essence of increasing the economic efficiency of the enterprise.

According to economists Ken Blanchard, Spencer Johnson [2] based on the consideration of different forms of production activity in management activities, it is effective in the following main factors: They believe that the level of interdependence between the human capital employed in the production process and the financial stimulation of human capital.

The company and any legal or physical entity that organizes the production process of the enterprise, to increase the efficiency of the personnel management that organizes the production and economic activities of the enterprise, to purchase production equipment and technologies necessary for the organization of production according to its directions. , providing them with raw

materials and offering human capital capable of responding to the organization and management of production according to their high qualification levels and creating the necessary infrastructures and their management on the basis of mutual cooperation with general production entities we believe that effective management of companies and enterprises can be achieved only by conducting.

As a result of the increase in the economic interest of each human capital employed in the production process of the enterprise, the collective production of the human capital employed in the production of the enterprise and the interdependence of their individual labor actions are the result of the team's we consider it to be of material interest.

In some cases, the invitation of highly qualified specialists to the production process of the enterprise does not lead to additional costs.

Because the result of labor activity in the production process of human capital involved in high-skilled production is higher than that of low-skilled human capital, and it achieves this by reducing the cost of production of a product with a higher value compared to its value.

When determining, or more precisely, evaluating the working abilities of employees, the enterprise should be based mainly on the following information:

- by the management for each employee, depending on their attitude to work and the quality of the work being performed;
- based on the positive attitude of the management towards the employee, that is, promotion or demotion to a higher position on the basis of taking into account their good work in their workplaces;
- it is necessary to determine the motivation of the employees according to the level and quality of the work performed by the management, or according to the punishment measures depending on the unsatisfactory performance of the work.

Effective or ineffective use of employees in industrial enterprises, it is necessary for the managers of the enterprise to pay attention to the following in order to organize the production process and make effective use of their working abilities.

Figure 1. Creation of conditions for effective personnel management at enterprises

The most important factor in the effective organization of the production process in enterprises is the creation of the necessary organizational economic mechanism in them. The fact

that every employee engaged in the production process is aware of the events taking place inside the enterprise, the production and economic activity of the enterprise ensures the effective organization of the production process. The level of efficiency of employees in enterprise production also depends on the level of organization of production and social infrastructures created for employees in their free time from production and production.

Some economists have proposed cost, income, expert and comparative approaches to quantify the value of human capital. In particular, the American scientist Jacques Fisens [3], the founder of the quantitative assessment of the value of human capital, considers the most difficult task to manage human activities by studying the main causes of labor productivity growth.

Although certain works on the study of the role of human capital in the organization of production and its values in developed countries have been and are being carried out, in our country, in the process of production of human capital in production enterprises, it is developed based on the requirements of market economy relations. It can be considered as a new direction to develop methods for quantitative assessment of its role and value in production. At the same time, methods based on different directions are known for calculating the value of human capital quantitatively. In the conditions of the market economy, the owner, who organizes the production of the enterprise, has the main goal of making a profit. The main way to maximize profit is based on the optimal ratio between the innovative organization of the material capital associated with production, and the investment funds spent on human capital and the growth of its intellectual capital levels. We consider that it depends on the quality levels of the goods produced, their unit cost and the level of competition in the consumer markets.

There are two ways to determine human capital based on the cost approach. The first method is the method of comparative comparison, which is determined by comparing the value of human capital based on the market value with the replacement value of this human capital. J. Tobin's coefficient [4] is used for this.

$$Q = \frac{R}{C} \quad (1)$$

Here R is the market value of human capital; C is defined as the replacement value of human capital.

Without denying that it is of practical importance in evaluating human capital in the form of value, this method can be determined using the income approach to evaluate the market value of human capital in the production process of an enterprise. In order to evaluate the replacement value of human capital in the production process of the enterprise, it is determined taking into account its operation in real conditions.

If the Tobin coefficient is equal to $q=1$, the investment value of human capital is equal to the investment potential of the enterprise.

Coefficient in determining the investment value of human capital

If $q < 1$ is less than 1, it means low investment attractiveness of the enterprise. The main reason for this is the fact that the potential of employees does not meet the demand, that is, it is low.

Also, when determining the investment cost of human capital, the significant coefficient (q) is greater than 1, to $q > 1$, so that the economically rated enterprise has the potential of highly qualified workers, the investment attractiveness of the enterprise is rated as high.

In addition to the proposed definition of human capital in the form of value, we believe that the involvement of human capital in the production process is important not only for the

intellectual level of the company's employees, but also for the quality of the capital in the form of the capital stock.

Quantitative assessment of human capital based on the income approach should take into account their full participation in creating the company's income.

The results of a comprehensive assessment for personnel management provide managers with information and analytical information for the systematic and continuous development of both individual employees and teams of departments in order to acquire new competencies necessary for development.

Based on the analyzes carried out to determine the effectiveness of personnel management in enterprises, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- employees are a human factor, expressed in the embodiment of his ability to work, the level of intellectual specialization and professional skills;
- efficient use of workers depends on the level of organization of social and production infrastructures necessary for their work;
- when determining the productivity of employees, it is necessary to rely on a single generalized evaluation system and evaluation methods.

In employee management, the comparison method is also used to evaluate their performance. With this method, you can identify bank personnel that provide good, average, and unsatisfactory service. But there are also negative aspects of this method, which create a discord between workers who work according to good, average and unsatisfactory needs.

The overall performance of enterprises, including reducing management costs and improving efficiency, is inextricably linked to the effectiveness of personnel management. In the conditions of market economic relations, the management of the enterprise and employees will increase each other's efficiency and ensure the achievement of the specified socio-economic indicators.

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